

Placement Prediction of Students Using the Data Mining Tool Weka

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Abstract— It would be great if some kind of support is given for students getting ready for the placement activities. Even though the placement officer provides much of the support for the students, so as to be prepared for the placements, it would be great if they can see where they stand and what are the steps to be taken to improve the chance of getting placed. There are certain factors that affect a student's placement like previous academic records, backlogs, communication skill etc.

In this study, student's data collected have different information about their previous and current academics records, so as to predicts the probability of student's getting placed in an IT company. In order to get to a conclusion, we consider the academic history of the student as well as their skill set like, programming skills, communication skills and teamwork, which are tested by the hiring companies during the recruitment process. And these factors predict the probability of students getting placed in a company.

Keywords-- Weka, accuracy, data mining, Naïve Bayes

I. INTRODUCTION

In a learning environment, placement is crucial. Many businesses depend heavily on campus recruiting to meet their needs [1]. Before they finish their schooling, the businesses select the skilled and eligible candidates. This approach is the most effective way to focus on the right opportunities at the right time in order to land good jobs early in their careers [2]. This is most likely to be accomplished using data mining concepts. The technique of data mining can be used for research and prediction. Weka, a data mining application, is being used to analyse the data in this analysis [3]. Data mining is a technique for finding patterns in large data sets that uses techniques from machine learning, statistics, and database systems.

The main goal was to assist students in obtaining a placement by identifying areas that they needed to change in order to obtain a placement. This method will have a significant effect on student success, resulting in improved academic outcomes, placements, and quality intake in institutes [1]. This system also makes it easier for teachers

to identify areas where students need to concentrate more often, improving their chances of being placed and the institute's credibility.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Eline Milne et al defined a method for effectively categorising the difficulty levels of learning various programming languages by undergraduate students in 2002 [2]. Ajay Sharma et al provided a model to classify the placement of students using a binary classification model of Logistic regression in Placement Prediction System Using Logistic Regression [3].

III. TOOL USED- WEKA

The goal of data mining tools is to find patterns, trends, and groupings in large sets of data and to turn the data into more refined knowledge [3]. It then allows for various forms of data mining work to be carried out. It can run algorithms on your data collection, such as clustering or classification, and visualise the effects.

WEKA is a data mining algorithm implementation method developed by the University of Waikato in New Zealand. WEKA is open-source software that is released under the GNU General Public License [10]. It includes tools for data preprocessing, machine learning algorithm implementation, and visualisation, allowing us to create machine learning techniques and apply them to real-world data mining problems.

Data preprocessing, clustering, classification, regression, visualisation, and feature selection are only a few of the typical data mining activities that Weka supports [9]. Weka's strategies are all based on the premise that the data is accessible as a single flat file or connection with a fixed number of attributes for each data point.

A. Features of Weka

- Weka is open source software licensed under the GNU General Public License [9].
- It comes with a graphical user interface (GUI).
- The command line has access to all of the software's functionality.

- Since it is written entirely in the Java programming language, it can run on nearly every modern computing platform.
- An extensive library of data preprocessing and modelling methods.
- Cross-platform compatibility
- Experiment scripting flexibility

B. History of Weka

- The original version of Weka, which was a mix of Tcl/Tk, C, and Makefiles, was started in 1993 at the University of Waikato in New Zealand [3].
- Weka's first non-Java edition was a Tcl/Tk frontend to (mostly third-party) modelling algorithms written in other programming languages, as well as data preprocessing utilities written in C and a Makefile-based framework for running machine learning experiments. This version was created with the aim of analysing data from agricultural domains [10].
- In 1997, the decision was taken to rewrite Weka in Java from the ground up, including modelling algorithm implementations.
- For the implementation of the publicly available Weka Data Mining Software, the Weka team won the SIGKDD Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery Service Award in 2005.
- The exclusive licence to use Weka for business intelligence was acquired by Pentaho Corporation in 2006. It is part of the Pentaho business intelligence suite's data mining and predictive analytics section. Hitachi Vantara has since acquired Pentaho, and Weka now powers the open source PMI (Plugin for Machine Intelligence) component [10].

C. Different Weka GUI choosers

- Data planning, function selection, and algorithm evaluation are all done in the explorer [9].
- Experient Environment for developing, running, and evaluating controlled experiment outcomes.
- KnowledgeFlow Environment, which allows developers to create and run machine learning pipelines graphically [10].
- Workbench, which combines all of Weka's software into a single, user-friendly GUI.
- A simple command-line interface for using the Weka API.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research is carried out in order to reach a meaningful conclusion. Before coming to a conclusion, we must demonstrate that our findings are right, and we must do so by demonstrating the same to others.

A. Primary data collection

Data can be collected in three different ways: qualitative data collection, quantitative data collection, and

triangulation [6]. The quantitative data collection approach is employed in this case. A questionnaire was created to conduct the primary data collection, which consists of 19 questions.

There must be 68 instances in the data obtained, and predictions will be made based on the data.

B. Questionnaire method

In order to collect primary data, a questionnaire that contains 19 questions was created. The information was then distributed among students in order to collect data, which could ultimately lead to a conclusion. Marks obtained in 10th, 12th, UG, PG, number of backlogs, as well as factors such as Communication Skills, Technical Skills, and Analytical Skills, which all play a role in the recruiting process, are some of the data variables considered for data classification [8].

The data collected would contain 68 examples, and the data will be used to make predictions.

C. Secondary data collection

The researcher gathers secondary data from books, journals, the internet, and other sources [6]. It is easier to collect secondary data than primary data, but the data would not be as up to date or reliable as primary data.

V. DATA ANALYSIS AND OBSERVATIONS

Forms were distributed to 100 students in order to collect data, and 68 students replied. Before the data is included in the study, it must first be analysed. The dataset contains 20 attributes, including marks obtained in 10th, 12th, UG, PG, number of backlogs, and several others, with a total of 68 instances [8]. As a result, 58 instances were used to train the dataset, with the remaining instances being used to evaluate it.

The model for classifying the probability of a student being put in this study is Naïve Bayes classification. For classification, there will be two options: true or false.

A. Naïve Bayes

Based on the Bayesian theorem, when the input dimensionality is high and a limited amount of training data is required, the Nave Bayes Algorithm is preferred. For a given class name, Naive Bayes presumed that all features are conditionally independent [4].

The collected data was analysed using the Naive Bayes classifier to determine whether or not a student will be placed.

Accuracy:-76.5%

Mean absolute error:- 0.3%

TABLE I. CONFUSION MATRIX FROM NAÏVE BAYES

Confusion Matrix		
<i>a</i>	<i>B</i>	←Classified as
6	14	a=FALSE
2	46	b=TRUE

Fig. 1. Confusion matrix from Naïve Bayes Method

The system was trained with 90% of the data collected, and the rest was used for research. Now those left out instances will come out handy to judge how reliable our method is when we get any new unknown data [5]. A class feature that predicts whether or not a student will be put.

Let's look at how the test dataset's input data predicts the value. Let's look at an example of a single data point from the collected dataset to see how it predicts the data. The sample 10 in the test dataset corresponds to this data. According to the analysis, the expected value is accurate with an error prediction of 0.694 based on the predicted test dataset.

TABLE II. SAMPLE DATA FROM THE DATASET

Variable name	Value
Highest qualification	MTech
History of backlogs	No
10 th percentage	92
12 th percentage	88
UG percentage	79
PG percentage	82
Number of backlogs	0
Courses to improve communication	Yes
Attended placement preparation programme	Yes
Time spend to prepare for aptitude on a weekly basis	5hrs
Attended practice tests regularly	Yes
Attend mock interviews	Yes
Opportunity for group discussions	Yes
Courses to improve programming skill	Yes
Number of projects undertaken	4
Number of seminars undertaken	3

Fig. 2. Data from Test dataset

After the model has been trained, it is saved and tested. The model is then re-evaluated on the test dataset using the saved model. If the forecast target class and the random target class are the same, the prediction margin is +1; otherwise, it is -1. All error prediction values are positive in this case, indicating that the prediction is accurate [10].

```

=== Predictions on user test set ===

inst#   actual  predicted error prediction
1       1:??   2:TRUE   0.694
2       1:??   2:TRUE   0.694
3       1:??   2:TRUE   0.694
4       1:??   2:TRUE   0.694
5       1:??   2:TRUE   0.694
6       1:??   2:TRUE   0.694
7       1:??   2:TRUE   0.694
8       1:??   2:TRUE   0.694
9       1:??   2:TRUE   0.694

```

Fig. 3. Prediction based on the test dataset

VI. CONCLUSION

A student's placement forecast gives them, as well as their teachers, an indication of where they stand. Various industries seek various skill sets. Students should be able to recognise their strengths and weaknesses so that they can plan appropriately[3]. This research also aids teachers in identifying areas where students need to focus on and guiding them in improving where they need to, thus raising their chances of being placed [8]. As a result, the key is to evaluate the student's abilities and provide them with the requisite preparation to perform at their best.

VII. REFERENCES

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